

Reasons for the rise of plastic pollution on the streets of Kampala and the existing measures that have been taken by Kampala City Council (KCCA).

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Abstract

Plastic waste management is one of the major environmental problems facing city municipalities today. In Kampala City, like other urban centers in Uganda, this important service is based on the local government's centralized collection, transportation and disposal strategy. Currently this approach has proved to be inefficient due to the heavy financial requirements involved. There is an urgent need to provide for the safe disposal of the plastic waste generated by urban residents and businesses. The increase in urban, economic and industrial activities, as well as the resultant population increase have led to an increase in the quantity of plastic waste generated. One method employed in collecting data included field trips to dump sites which are used by the Kampala City Council Authority (KCC). Monitoring of collection points both in the Central Business areas and in residential areas was also used. Interviews were conducted on personnel, both in the Kampala City Council Authority (KCCA) and on residents in high, medium and low density residential areas. The results of the study indicate that alternative means to plastic disposal need to be developed with population growth and economic development in mind. This study is an attempt to analyze the management options that the KCC has and how effective our Automated Plastic Disposal system will be.

1.0. Introduction

The status of Plastic waste management in Kampala, just like in other urban centers in the country, is unhygienic and unsatisfactory. Plastic waste management in the city is the responsibility of KCCA.

Group 46 members made a survey to investigate the current plastic waste management methods used by KCCA. Below are some of the problems we encountered during the study.

1. Inaccurate data.
2. Inadequate funding.
3. Lack of trust by data providers.
4. Research demands a lot of time and effort.

2.0. Related work

The Kampala Capital City Authority (KCCA) has installed more garbage bins along the streets to ease garbage collection [1]. The bins are designed to accommodate recyclable [2] and non-recyclable waste materials that people of Kampala keep throwing around, littering the city. The project was currently being piloted in the central business district with at least 1,000 garbage bins planned for installation around the city suburbs and surrounding area.

According to the KCCA annual report on solid waste collection and disposal for financial year 2011/2012 [3], Kampala generates an estimated 1,500 tonnes of garbage daily, and over the years, KCCA has been able to pick up only 500 tonnes a day. According to the report, the average garbage collection in Kampala stood at 29,543 tonnes per month as at end of June, 2012 from 16,000 in April 2011. So this pilot project should be welcome. The installation of garbage bins in the city is not new though; Nasser Sebagala [4], a former city mayor, installed such bins in the city. However, the discipline of the city dwellers leaves a lot to be desired. Even with the bins, some people would still toss the rubbish just besides the bin. And this is where the challenge lies. According to the Authority spokesperson Peter Kauju [5], KCCA has partnered with private companies to implement the bin project. This planned and well-formulated public-private partnership arrangement as KCCA says, should be fully exploited to realize a clean and habitable city.

Although KCCA has partnered with private companies to collect solid waste, only a small fraction of the waste generated is collected and this suggests inefficiency in the solid waste management system. So the Authority needs to put under scrutiny how best this is going to work.

Previously, over 815 litter bins were distributed in the central business district, schools and hospitals to promote responsible solid waste management [6], with punitive measures accompanying for those who litter the city intentionally. Now with this new garbage strategy introduced, there is need for community involvement through sensitization of the city dwellers to achieve the objective for which it is set [7].

As one of the ways to better manage garbage disposal and improve hygiene in the city, Kampala Capital City Authority has revamped its ‘Keep Kampala Clean’ campaign [8]. While launching the community service in Ndeeba in Rubaga division, KCCA’s director of public health David Sserugo [9] said the mass cleaning exercises will be carried out in all divisions every last Friday of the month. They were aiming at reducing rubbish in the city which is still in plenty. This means that the high numbers of people that spend money in hospitals will reduce.

Eliab Kyagoba [8], a local council leader in Ndeeba, hailed KCCA and residents for cleaning up their area. In the same spirit, he appealed to KCCA to always work with residents in all they are doing as it was with the ‘Keep Kampala Clean’ campaign to enable smooth running of the work in the city. Residents worked together with KCCA officials and swept streets in the area, cleaned up drainage channels, emptied latrines and sprayed insects.

Much as people actively participated in this at first the process is phasing out in most parts of Kampala. This only leaves more plastic litters in waters sources, wetlands this can be viewed in areas of bwise, kalerwe and other slum areas. This has come up since KCCA doesn’t offer anything in return to those who actively participate. Considering the current effort both from KCCA and residents done to curb plastic litters we strongly believe that our proposed system will play a big role value towards achieving the goal of reducing plastic waste in Kampala areas. According to our survey especially in business centers, people were in full support of such a proposal because of the personal benefits involved apart from reducing litters around them.

3.0. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The research method used the in this study is a descriptive research design which is a study designed to depict the participants in an accurate way. This was of a survey type.

This method was used because of;

1. Its effectiveness to analyze non-quantified topics and issues
2. Capable of collecting data from a large number of respondents Numerous questions can be asked about a subject, giving extensive flexibility in data analysis
3. Standardized surveys are relatively free from several types of errors

3.2.Study Population.

The study involved 10 KCCA staff members, 20 random people around Kampala including 10 business personnel, and 10 residents.

3.3.Sampling technique

The method of sample selection was simple random sampling this means each member of the population has an equal and independent chance of being selected to be part of the sample.

3.4.Research Instrument.

The research instrument used was an interview guide. An interview is the verbal conversation between two people with the objective of collecting relevant information for the purpose of research.

3.5.Data Collection.

Two Interview guides were developed one for the KCCA staff members and the other guide for the rest of the target population. On the basis of the objective drawn up for the survey, output tables for analysis have been developed.

4.0. Results (Survey Findings)

4.1.Findings from KCCA staff members (sample size 10)

Who is responsible for the plastic waste increase in Kampala?	No. of KCCA officers with the same view.
Increasing number of beverage companies in Uganda.	2
Beverage companies shifting from glass bottle to plastic bottle packaging	2
Limited number of recycling companies	1
People's negligence of not using the dustbins	5

The following are the measures taken by KCCA to curb plastic in Kampala. All this was provided by KCCA staff members

1. Distribution of garbage cans around the city.
2. KCCA employs workers to clean the city both roads and trenches.
3. KCCA partner with different garbage collecting companies
4. KCCA campaign “keep the city green”. Which urges residents to always drop plastic wastes in their rightful places.
5. KCCA warning notes of “don’t dispose of garbage here” where they fine the culprits

6. KCCA donates garbage collecting teens in school, Hospitals and business centers

Methods used to curb plastic litter in the city	Most used according to KCCA staff members
Distribution of garbage cans around the city.	3
KCCA employs workers to clean the city both roads and trenches.	6
KCCA donates garbage collecting teens in school, Hospitals and business centres	0
KCCA campaign “keep the city green”. Which urges residents to always drop plastic wastes in their rightful places	1
KCCA warning notes of “don’t dispose of garbage here” where they fine the culprits	0

Most costly method	No. of views from KCCA members
Distribution of garbage cans around the city.	3
KCCA employs workers to clean the city both roads and trenches.	6
KCCA donates garbage collecting teens in school, Hospitals and business centres	1
KCCA campaign “keep the city green”. Which urges residents to always drop plastic wastes in their rightful places	0

Do you think our proposed system will curb plastic pollution in Kampala?	No of Views by KCCA members
YES	7
NO	3

The following are the views about the functionality of the proposed system	Number of KCCA members with the same view
I think the functionality will work because it will inspire people to appropriately dispose of plastic in the rightful place	4
It will work because it will cater for a larger population because of the benefits.	2
It will work because it's more organised than the current means.	1
It will save KCCA man power invested in cleaning the city	3

Do you think the system is costly according to the current budget of KCCA?	Number of KCCA members with the same view
YES	4
NO	6

4.2. Findings from residents and business personnel (sample size 20)

Methods used to curb plastic litter in the city	Most used methods in their areas
Distribution of garbage cans around the city.	5

KCCA employs workers to clean the city both roads and trenches.	12
KCCA donates garbage collecting teens in school, Hospitals and business centres	1
KCCA campaign “keep the city green”. Which urges residents to always drop plastic wastes in their rightful places	2
KCCA warning notes of “don’t dispose of garbage here” where they fine the culprits	0

These are some of the responses we received on why people have not fully responded to KCCA garbage collection methods such as garbage tins

1. Garbage cans are not accessible in most areas.
2. People are not aware of the dangers plastic pollution in an environment.

Garbage/plastic collecting methods used in their areas.

1. Distribution of dust bins
2. KCCA garbage collecting trucks
3. KCCA Garbage cleaners

Most effective methods.

Methods	Most effective
Distribution of dust bins	11
KCCA garbage collecting trucks	3
KCCA Garbage cleaners	6

Do you think our proposed system will help curb plastics?

YES	15
NO	5

5.0.Recommendations

The increase in plastic wastes around the city of Kampala is becoming an issue. Most beverage companies are shifting from Glass bottle packaging to Plastic bottle packaging. This means an increase of plastic wastes in Kampala and responsible bodies should come up with better methods to curb the increase of plastic litters. As a result we strongly believe that the introduction of our system will help to reduce on the problem.

6.0. Conclusion

From the above study it is observed that most people are not fully aware of the threats plastic pollution can do an environment. The study also indicates that the current garbage collection methods are have not fully been responded to by the people which still leaves plastic litters all over the city.

7.0. Future work

Our future work is to come up with a feasible solution that will aim to reduce on plastic litter in the city. Perhaps an automated system that is aimed at rewarding plastic disposers every time they reach the required points for a reward.

References

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